

Science, Magic, and Scandal. 60 years of Tibetan Buddhism in the West

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Introduction

The case of Tibetan Vajrayāna Buddhism in the West is particular in that it does not easily fit into categories such as post-traditional or post-secular. Having been forced into modernity¹ only as late as the 1950s, with the invasion of Tibet by Chinese forces, and with the separation between religion and state only being accomplished in 2011,² Tibetan Buddhism today forms a bewildering mix of, on the one hand, claims of modernism, rationalism and compatibility with science, and on the other, pre-modern beliefs and practices that appear somewhat medieval, and that involve what appears magical and miraculous. Recently, there have been several widely publicised scandals and allegations of abuse, which, I will argue, can be understood as the result of a failure to distinguish

1 That there was an explicit drive by the Chinese government to bring Tibetan Buddhism into modernity can be seen in the comments made in 1951 by the editor-in-chief of the Beijing-run journal *Modern Buddhism* (*Hsien-tai fo-hsüeh*): Buddhists who do not accept (the New Democracy) are either reactionaries or backward elements. Reactionaries have no political rights; backward elements do not understand the times... Only if they become progressive and join the people of the era of the New Democracy can they fully enjoy all the freedoms of the Common Program... Some Buddhists think that, because the Common Program provides for freedom of belief, they can do anything they like and that anyone who corrects their thinking or actions is infringing on their freedom of religion. This is a very big mistake and really is the thinking of backward elements. Cited in Holmes Welch, *Buddhism under Mao* (Cambridge MA: Harvard University Press, 1972), 6–7. See also Melvyn C. Goldstein, “Introduction,” in *Buddhism in Contemporary Tibet: Religious Revival and Cultural Identity*, eds. Melvyn C. Goldstein and Matthew T. Kapstein (London: University of California Press, 1998), 2–3.

2 Jim Yardley and Edward Wong, “Dalai Lama Gives up Political Role,” *The New York Times*, March 10, 2011, <https://www.nytimes.com/2011/03/11/world/asia/11tibet.html>.

between different forms of Buddhism in the West, and a misinterpretation of the guru-student relationship.

This article will outline the history of Buddhism's spread in the West, highlighting some of the biggest scandals and cases of abuse to emerge in global Tibetan Buddhist institutes. It will examine the notions of guru devotion and crazy wisdom, which seem to underlie these occurrences, by bringing up examples from Tibetan hagiographies. I will suggest that abuse is occurring because there is no clear distinction made between Tibetan Vajrayāna Buddhism and other forms of Buddhism, and many novices enter the Vajrayāna unwittingly, or at least they think they do, and do not understand what is expected of them as students of a particular teacher. Finally, I will make some tentative suggestions for moving forward and avoiding similar misunderstandings in the future.

First, however, a few words about terminology are warranted. Tibetan Buddhism contains much that is known, in Sanskrit, as 'Vajrayāna,' 'Tantrayāna' or 'Mantrayāna,'³ in distinction from other more widely known forms of Buddhism sometimes called the Hīnayāna (e.g. Theravāda) and the Mahāyāna.⁴

3 The term 'Vajrayāna,' although more commonly used today, is a later term for tantric Buddhism, and refers to the Thunderbolt or Diamond Weapon of Indra (S. *vajra*), implying that the 'vehicle' (*yāna*) is indestructible. The term '*tantra*' refers to a group of texts whereas a '*mantra*' is a sacred sound, syllable, or utterance used to evoke the tantric deities and gain their blessings. Apart from texts and mantras, the Vajrayāna also makes use of *mudrā*, that is, gestures and postures that are usually physical.

4 Hīnayāna Buddhism consists of what has generally been held to be the earliest form of Buddhism, found in the canonical texts written in Pāli, and practiced in places like Thailand, Myanmar and Sri Lanka. For this reason, it is also referred to as Southern Buddhism. Because 'Hīnayāna' translates as 'small vehicle,' the term is often seen as pejorative, and thus the term *Nikāya* Buddhism (referring to the texts of the Pāli canon) or *Theravāda* Buddhism (the path of the elders) is preferred. Tibetan Buddhists refer to the Hīnayāna as *Śrāvakayāna* (vehicle of the hearers) and *Pratyekabuddhayāna* (vehicle of the solitary Buddhas) and accept both as important foundations of their own faith. However, the Vajrayāna is held to be a Mahāyāna path. The Mahāyāna was generally held to be a later Buddhist tradition, which differs from Pāli Buddhism in that its canon is written in Sanskrit rather than Pāli and in its emphasis on the *bodhisattva* ('awakening one') ideal. The bodhisattva, unlike the *arahant* of the Pāli canon, postpones his or her enlightenment until all sentient beings are saved. The Mahāyāna is practiced in China, Japan, Korea, and Vietnam and thus is also known as Eastern Buddhism. Much of Tibetan Buddhism is identical to these forms of Mahāyāna Buddhism. However, Tibetan Buddhism also contains tantric elements (see note 2 above), rendering it unlike most other forms of Buddhism. Today, the categorization of Buddhism into the three main vehicles of Hīnayāna, Mahāyāna and Vajrayāna has been called into question by the rediscovery of Buddhist manuscripts written in a third language, Gāndhārī, which are the oldest known extant manuscripts, and which seem to contain elements of both Hīnayāna and Mahāyāna. In fact, it is now accepted

Tibetan Buddhism is a form of Mahāyāna Buddhism, which differs from other Mahāyāna traditions in that it includes, besides texts held to be words spoken by the Buddha (S. *sūtra*; P. *sutta*) and commentaries on these (S. *śāstra*), various other texts known as ‘*tantra*’ (S.), that is, texts dating from the 6th Century C.E. that contain meditative and ritualistic methods similar to those found in Śaivite Hinduism.⁵

Tibetan tantric Buddhism relies heavily on devotion to the teacher, the *guru* (S.) or *lama* (T.; W. *bla ma*), which can refer to any kind of spiritual teacher or even any grade of monastic, but is usually reserved for those with realisation. I will use the words ‘teacher,’ ‘lama’ and ‘guru’ interchangeably. A *tülku* (W. *sprul sku*; S. *nirmāṇakāya*) is the recognized reincarnation of a well-known lama. There are hundreds of *tülkus* living outside Tibet today, almost all male, and these recognized reincarnations are usually taken away from their families and into a monastery at a very young age, to begin a system of intense training, with frequent public appearances and a formal enthronement, which can occur as early as the age of three.

Tibetan Buddhism in the West

Apart from the traditional division into Hīnayāna, Mahāyāna and Vajrayāna, it is widely accepted that there are two “Weberian ideal types” of Buddhism existent today in the West.⁶ The story has often been told of how what might be described as a lack of confidence on both Eastern and Western sides led to Buddhism being portrayed, in the late 19th and early 20th Centuries, as more rational and scientific than the colonisers’ Christian faith.⁷ Much is made of the

that many forms of Buddhism existed from a very early period in its history, “each with its own distinctive literature and canon.” Richard Salomon, *The Buddhist Literature of Ancient Gandhāra: An Introduction with Selected Translations*, (Somerville, MA: Wisdom Publications, 2018), 57.

5 Maria Iontseva, “Mutual Borrowing Between the Yogic and Meditation Practices of Tantric Śaivism and Vajrayāna Buddhism” (master’s thesis, University of London, 2021).

6 Martin Baumann, “Global Buddhism: Developmental Periods, Regional Histories, and a New Analytical Perspective,” *Journal of Global Buddhism* no 2, (2001): 25.

7 In Asia, in response to colonialism and missionary Christianity, Buddhist reformers and delegates to the West, such as Anagārika Dharmapāla (1864–1933) presented Buddhism as a rational faith compatible with modern science. This message was taken up by European and American scholars and converts, in part due to what has been termed the “Victorian crisis of faith.” David L. McMahan, *The Making of Buddhist Modernism*, (New York: Oxford University Press, 2008), 95–107.

fact that there is no reference to a Creator or Interventionist God in Buddhism,⁸ but rather, that all events are explained in terms of karma, which is a natural process of cause and effect.⁹ Seemingly mythical elements in traditional Buddhist cosmology, such as the existence of various heavens and hells, were secularized and explained as psychological states¹⁰ and it was emphasised that the Buddha encouraged his listeners not to accept any doctrine on blind faith, but rather to test it empirically for themselves.¹¹ The Buddha, in short, was

8 For instance: In the Ethics of the Happy Home which the Blessed One enunciated there was no place for a despotic god who goeth against immutable laws. The gospel of self help is the profound doctrine which the Buddha proclaimed. To do the will of a Creator means to conform to the foolishness of a pagan prophet who proclaimed the idea...A despotic creator and a dogma asserting that man is fated to go through a predestinated course rob man of his power to individualised activity in harmony with the law of Cause and Effect (that is, karma). Anagārika Dharmapala, *The Arya Dharma of Sakya Muni, Gautama, Buddha or The Ethics of Self Discipline* (Calcutta: Maha Bodhi Society, 1917), 56.

9 For instance: The Blessed One after having gained Omniscience found that there is neither a permanency nor an annihilation of existence; but a continuous change depending on the law of cause and effect according to the good or evil karma. *Ibid.*, 56.

10 Most famous among psychological interpretations of Buddhism is Carl Jung's commentary on the *Bardo Thödol*, better known as *The Tibetan Book of the Dead*. In his words: Its philosophy contains the quintessence of Buddhist psychological criticism; and, as such, one can truly say that it is of an unexampled superiority. Not only the 'wrathful' but also the 'peaceful' deities are conceived as... projections of the human psyche, an idea that seems all too obvious to the enlightened European, because it reminds him of his own banal simplifications. But though the European can easily explain away these deities as projections, he would be quite incapable of positing them at the same time as real. The *Bardo Thödol* can do that, because, in certain of its most essential metaphysical premises, it has the enlightened as well as the unenlightened European at a disadvantage. The ever-present, unspoken assumption of the *Bardo Thödol* is the antinomial character of all metaphysical assertions, and also the idea of the qualitative difference of the various levels of consciousness and of the metaphysical reality conditioned by them. The background of this unusual book is not the niggardly European 'either-or,' but a magnificently affirmative 'both-and.' Carl Jung, *Psychological Commentary on W. Y. Evans-Wentz, in The Tibetan Book of the Dead or The After-Death Experiences on the Bardo Plane, according to Lama Kazi Dawa-Samdup's English Rendering*, 3rd ed., (London: Oxford University Press, 1957), xxxvii.

11 The source of this claim is the *Kālāma Sutta*, a text in the Pāli canon where the Buddha exhorts his listeners, the Kalamas: Do not go upon what has been acquired by repeated hearing; nor upon tradition; nor upon rumour; nor upon what is in a scripture; nor upon surmise; nor upon an axiom; nor upon specious reasoning; nor upon a bias towards a notion that has been pondered over; nor upon another's seeming ability; nor upon the consideration, "The monk is our teacher." Kalamas, when you yourselves know: "These things are good; these things are not blameable; these things are praised by the wise; undertaken and observed, these things lead to benefit and happiness," enter on and abide in them. *Anguttara Nikāya* 3.65, trans. Soma Thera, "Kālāma Sutta," Access to Insight, <https://www.accesstoinsight.org/lib/authors/soma/wheel008.html>. Commenting on a reading of this sutta in Colombo, Sri Lanka in 1906, the American minister Moncure D. Conway (1832–1907) put it

presented by the first delegates to the West as entirely modern in his thinking, even as a scientist equal to Newton¹² and thus the most common perception of Buddhism in the West today is of something that is rational, that can be tested empirically, and packaged into a mindfulness app.

Asian Buddhists who migrated to the West brought a somewhat different understanding of their faith, with many seeking to continue the devotional activities they most closely associated with spiritual practice. Asian migrants often brought along with them, not so much meditation or mindfulness, but rather: giving alms to the clergy, observing lunar festivals, making offerings to representations of the Buddha and other unmodern practices. All of this is held to increase merit (*S. punya*; *T. sonam*; *W. bsod nams*; also ‘virtue’) which ensures a good rebirth, and from its very beginnings, Buddhism contained elements of what appears to be magic, such as belief in mind-reading and miraculous displays, engaged in for worldly as well as spiritual pursuits.¹³ Thus, it can be said that there were, in the West, “two Buddhisms,” which mostly remained separate until after WWII.¹⁴

Tibetan Buddhism only became well-known in the West after the Chinese occupation in the 1950s; before that, the few Western accounts of Tibet that existed were, if not highly negative, mostly fraudulent, or misinformed. From Marco Polo onwards, European commentators in general regarded Tibetans as superstitious and uneducated, their religion nothing but demonic idolatry. Even towards the start of the 20th Century, European scholars still claimed that the Tibetan faith was not really Buddhist but ‘Lamaist,’ described as a medieval and feudal theocratic system, where despotic god-kings known as the Dalai Lama ruled, often inflicting great violence and suffering on the people. Positive portrayals came mainly from the Theosophical Society, especially Alexandra David-Neel, who claimed to have visited Tibet in 1924. The authenticity of

as follows: “To me, indeed, it was thrilling that from a past of seventy generations should come this voice summoning man to rest his faith on his own reason, and trust his life for eternity to virtues rooted in his own consciousness.” Moncure D. Conway, *My Pilgrimage to the Wise Men of the East*, (Cambridge MA: The Riverside Press, 1906), 133.

12 McMahan, *The Making of Buddhist Modernism*, 90.

13 Ra Yeshé Sengé, introduction to *The all-pervading melodious drumbeat. The life of Ra Lotsawa*, trans. Bryan J Cuevas, (New York: Penguin Books, 2015), xix.; See also Sam van Schaik, *Buddhist Magic: Divination, Healing, and Enchantment through the Ages*. (Boulder, Colorado: Shambhala Publications, 2020).

14 Prebish, Charles S., *American Buddhism*, (Massachusetts: Duxbury Press, 1979), 51.

this and other early twentieth century works extolling Tibetan Buddhism is, however, strongly doubted.¹⁵

During the 1960s and 70s, after his escape from Tibet and with the help of some Western supporters, the Dalai Lama and his office succeeded in raising and improving the profile of Tibetan Buddhism in the popular imagination. The Dalai Lama was awarded the Nobel Peace Prize in 1989, and became a highly visible figure, invited, if not in official capacity as temporal leader of Tibet, to participate as a distinguished guest in spiritual, environmental and even scientific conferences around the world. In 2005 he was invited to address thousands of neuroscientists,¹⁶ and over the last six decades has collaborated strongly with scientists, especially through the Mind and Life Institute, in what appears to be an attempt to modernize Tibetan Buddhism.¹⁷

Thus, although students are often introduced to Tibetan Buddhism as a modern and rational system, mainly through mindfulness courses, it is not long before they encounter various pre-modern practices in Tibetan institutions, such as students prostrating before the lama. This is because Tibetan Buddhism, as a Vajrayāna path, builds upon the earlier systems of Buddhism. Thus, while it includes all of the earlier monastic Hīnayāna Buddhist teachings that are taken to be the source of modern, scientific Buddhism, as well as the seemingly magical practices of the lay followers of traditional, pre-colonial Hīnayāna and Mahāyāna Buddhism, it also includes Vajrayāna elements that require guru devotion, hence its earlier English name, Lamaism.

Other lamas who left Tibet at the same time as the Dalai Lama went on to establish important Buddhist institutions in Europe and America. Most notable among these are Chögyam Trungpa and Sogyal Lakar, whose respective institutions Vajradhatu (later Shambhala) and Rigpa were both subject to multiple scandals and serious allegations of abuse. For the sake of brevity, this article will focus on these two International Buddhist organisations; however, it

15 Donald S. Lopez, Jr., *Prisoners of Shangri-La: Tibetan Buddhism and the West*, (London: The University of Chicago Press, 1998), 15–114.

16 Yudhijit Bhattacharjee, “Neuroscientists Welcome Dalai Lama With Mostly Open Arms,” *Science* 310, no. 5751 (November 2005), <https://www.science.org/doi/10.1126/science.310.5751.1104>

17 Jens Schlieter, “REVIEW.” Review of *The Monastery and the Microscope: Conversations with the Dalai Lama on Mind, Mindfulness, and the Nature of Reality*, ed. Wendy Hasenkamp and Janna R. White, *Reading Religion*, January 15, 2018, <https://readingreligion.org/9780300218084/the-monastery-and-the-microscope/>

is worth noting that other Tibetan and non-Tibetan Buddhist institutions have been subject to similar scandals.

Shambhala International

Originally named Vajradhatu International, this organisation began in 1973 in Boulder, Colorado, and was founded by Chögyam Trungpa. Trungpa also founded a university there, the Naropa institute, which styles itself as “the birthplace of the modern mindfulness movement.”¹⁸ As is well known, the practice of mindfulness today is regarded as a scientific and evidence-based form of therapy, and has been secularised to the extent that it often contains no reference to Buddhism at all.

Vajradhatu attracted many celebrities; Allen Ginsberg, Gary Snyder, William Burroughs, John Cage, and David Bowie among many others.¹⁹ In 1975, the poet W.S. Merwyn and his girlfriend Dana Naone became involved in what was probably the first widely publicised scandal in any Western Tibetan Buddhist organisation. According to witness accounts, during a Halloween party at an “Intensive Training Seminar,” after being violently brought down to the party at Trungpa’s orders, Merwyn and Naone were forcibly stripped. After that party, Merwyn and Naone stayed on for another three weeks, and no charges were brought. However, the incident led to a widely publicised disagreement between Merwyn and Ginsberg, because the latter would not renounce Trungpa.²⁰

Eleven years later, Trungpa moved Vajradhatu to Halifax, Nova Scotia and more than six hundred families followed him.²¹ He died the following year, at the age of 48, as a result of his heavy drinking. The next leader was his appointed regent, Ösel Tendzin (Thomas Rich), infamous today for having had unprotected sexual encounters while knowing that he was infected with H.I.V..²²

18 Leland Radovanovic, “Naropa University, Birthplace of the Modern Mindfulness Movement, Celebrates 50 Years of Transformative Education,” *Businesswire* (2024), accessed 24 April 2025, <https://www.businesswire.com/news/home/20240625813514/en/Naropa-University-Birthplace-of-the-Modern-Mindfulness-Movement-Celebrates-50-Years-of-Transformative-Education>

19 Christine A. Chandler, *Enthralled: The Guru Cult of Tibetan Buddhism*, (self-pub., BookBaby, 2018), 94–95.

20 Ed Sanders, “The Party: a chronological Perspective on a confrontation at a Buddhist Seminary,” *Boulder Monthly*, insert number of journal (March 1979): 25–39.

21 Jamyang Khyentse, *The Guru Drinks Bourbon?* (Shambhala, 2016), 63.

22 Stephen T. Butterfield, *The Double Mirror: A Skeptical Journey into Buddhist Tantra* (Berkeley, CA: North Atlantic Books, 1994), 4–6.

After all this emerged in 1989, Tendzin formed a separate organisation with some of his students and Vajradhatu continued until it was renamed Shambhala International in 2000 by its new leader, Sakyong Mipham, Trungpa's son. Sakyong remained at the head of Shambhala until 2018, when he had to step down due to allegations of sexual misconduct.²³

Thus, although the party scandal came to light decades ago, abuse in Shambhala continues to be exposed. Today, Shambhala Global is run by a Board of Directors, who, in their documentation stated that no replacement is being sought for Sakyong Mipham and instead “a collaborative decision-making process... outside of Sakyong Mipham Rinpoche's direct teaching” was being devised.²⁴ Despite these scandals, Shambhala remains strong as a global institution and claims to have more than 150 centres and groups in over 50 countries and on all continents.²⁵

Rigpa International

Rigpa International is another global Tibetan Buddhist institution, with 117 Dharma centres in 24 countries and two large retreat centres in Europe.²⁶ It was founded by Sogyal Lakar (a.k.a. Sogyal Rinpoche)²⁷ in 1979 and was originally based in London. When he first arrived in the UK, Sogyal Lakar received support from Mary Finnegan, a journalist who had been introduced to Tibetan Buddhism by David Bowie. Yet, in 2021 she co-authored, with Rob Hogendoorn, a book entitled *Sex and Violence in Tibetan Buddhism; The Rise and Fall of Sogyal Rinpoche*, in which she details her experiences.

Sogyal Lakar was born in Tibet in 1947 and fled the Chinese occupation in 1955 with his family and father-figure Jamyang Khyentse Chöki Lodrö. The

23 Andy Newman, “The ‘King’ of Shambhala Buddhism Is Undone by Abuse Report,” *The New York Times*, July 11, 2018, accessed 20 April 2025, <https://www.nytimes.com/2018/07/11/nyregion/shambhala-sexual-misconduct.html>

24 Shambhala, “Shambhala FAQs – Working File,” *Shambhala* (2023), accessed 15 April 2025, <https://shambhala.org/files/2023/06/Shambhala-Board-FAQs.pdf>

25 Shambhala, “Shambhala Centres and Groups,” *Shambhala*, accessed 15 April 2025, <https://shambhala.org/centres/centres-groups/>

26 Rigpa, “Where we are,” *Rigpa*, <https://www.rigpa.org/locations>.

27 The honorific term ‘Rinpoche’ (W. *rin po che*) means ‘precious one,’ and is reserved for recognized tülkus and teachers. Due to the controversy regarding Sogyal, it has become customary to refer to him by his family name Lakar. My choice in using this appellation is intended merely to convey neutrality and not as a judgement of Sogyal.

latter was known as a great lama and became the head of the monastery in Sikkim, India, where they all took up residence. He had recognized Sogyal, the child of one of his consorts (T. *sangyum*; W. *gsang yum*),²⁸ as the reincarnation of the great mystic and treasure revealer (T. *tertön*; W. *gter ston*)²⁹ Lerab Lingpa Trinlé Thayé Tsal, or Tertön Sogyal,³⁰ however, he seems to have failed to make provisions for the young tulku's training. Sogyal in fact received a Christian education in India, and went on to Cambridge to study comparative religion, although he did not graduate. An alternative story that Finnegan relates is that Sogyal originally went to the U.K as a companion to Prince Tenzin Namgyal of Sikkim, so that both could receive treatment for tuberculosis.³¹

Sogyal Lakar and the Dalai Lama seem to have met in Sikkim, at the beginning of the Tibetan exodus, when the Dalai Lama was in his twenties, and Sogyal a pre-teen. The Dalai Lama also visited Sogyal in London during his first visit to the West in 1973 and would go on to write the foreword to Sogyal's book, *The Tibetan Book of Living and Dying*, published in 1992. The book became a best seller and turned Sogyal into a household name.

In 1994, Sogyal had an important role in Bertolucci's *Little Buddha*, catapulting his fame further. Starring Keanu Reeves as the Buddha, the movie is about the recognition of a young American boy as the reincarnation of the teacher of Sogyal's character. That was also the year the first civil lawsuit for "sexual and emotional abuse" against Sogyal was filed and settled out of court.³²

28 It is not unusual for Tibetan lamas to have multiple consorts, one or more of which may be their spouse. Guru Padmasambhava (see below) had five consorts. Female lamas, although rare, may also have one or more male consorts.

29 A treasure revealer is a highly qualified lama who discovers treasures that had been hidden away by Guru Padmasambhava and his Tibetan consort Yeshe Tsogyal, to be rediscovered in the future dark ages. These treasures (T. *ter*; W. *gTer*) may be either physical objects and texts, literally, 'Earth Treasures' (T. *sa ter*; W. *sa gTer*), or else they are discovered by the tertön "by awakening the mind-mandated transmission spontaneously from the expanse of intrinsic awareness of his mind, when the circumstances have matured and the time has come." Tulku Thondup, "The Terma Tradition of the Nyingmapa School," *The Tibet Journal*, 15, no. 4 (1990), 157.

30 Whether or not Sogyal Lakar was really recognized is debated. For a more nuanced account, see Bernd Zander, "Knowns and Unknowns Regarding Sogyal Rinpoche's Biography," *Buddhism Controversy Blog*, October 7, 2019. <https://buddhism-controversy-blog.com/2019/10/07/knowns-and-unknowns-regarding-sogyal-rinpoche-biography/>.

31 Mary Finnegan and Rob Hogendoorn, *Sex and Violence in Tibetan Buddhism: The Rise and Fall of Sogyal Rinpoche*, (Portland OR: Jorvik Press, 2021).

32 Richard Sandomir, "Sogyal Rinpoche Dies; Tibetan Buddhist Lama Felled by Abuse Accusations," *New York Times*, September 1, 2019, <https://www.nytimes.com/2019/09/01/obituaries/sogyal-rinpoche-dies.html>

More than 20 years later, in 2017, eight former members of Rigpa raised allegations against Sogyal, with some complaining that the abuse had gone on for decades. Citing the Dalai Lama, who in 1993, had publicly given Vajrayāna students the permission to leave abusive teachers and to expose their wrongdoings, stating unequivocally that this does not amount to a breach in *samaya*,³³ these students accused Sogyal of physical, emotional, psychological and sexual abuse and of living a “lavish, gluttonous, and sybaritic lifestyle,” as well as of tainting the Dharma.³⁴ Sogyal retired from Rigpa a few weeks later, after the Dalai Lama spoke of him as being ‘disgraced,’ and died two years later of a pulmonary embolism.

Guru Devotion and Crazy Wisdom

Both of these institutions were able to cover up the abuse for so long and to overcome such scandals through the efforts of an inner circle of devotees, most of whom came from Western, liberal, secular and highly educated backgrounds. There is evidence that, in each case, not only were these closest students aware of the abuse, they seem to have explained it away as a display of ‘crazy wisdom.’³⁵ What this means, in brief, is that abusive behaviour by the lama is to be interpreted as a blessing; the lama is not really angry or violent, but is using ‘skilful methods’ (*S. upāyakauśalya*; T. *thab kye*; W. *thabs mkhas*) for purifying the students’ negative karma in order to lead them to Buddhahood. Thinking otherwise is due to impure vision and amounts to breach in one’s tantric commitments, which can only lead to hell.³⁶

33 *S. samaya*; T. *damtshig*; W. *dam tshig*, a set of commitments or vows, most important of which is to regard one’s Vajrayāna lama as an enlightened being, and never to disparage or go against him or her.

34 Mark Standlee et. al. “Letter to Sogyal Lakar,” *Lionsroar*, July 14, 2017, accessed 20 April 2025, <https://www.lionsroar.com/wp-content/uploads/2017/07/Letter-to-Sogyal-Lakar-14-06-2017-.pdf>, 3

35 Corresponding terms in Tibetan include ‘crazy lama’ (T. *lama nyonpa*; W. *bla ma smyon pa*); also ‘crazy accomplished master’ (T. *drupthob nyonpa*; W. *grub thob smyon pa*) which is often shortened to *drupnyon*.

36 For example, some students of Ösel Tendzin seem to have linked the H.I.V scandal to “the risks inherent in Trungpa Rinpoche’s crazy wisdom tradition (see below), which included outrageous and unconventional behaviour as part of its repertoire.” Rick Fields and Benjamin Bogin, *How the swans came to the lake: A narrative history of Buddhism in America*, (Boulder, CO: Shambhala Publications, 2022), 426. Disillusioned students go further, describing Tibetan Buddhism as a cult, where highly educated Westerners are threatened with “Vajra Hell” and “programmed to look away and deny the exploitation; even sexual abuse, as though none of it was taking place” for fear of committing a “root downfall,” that is, “speaking ill of the Tibetan lamas who are to become your vajra masters and (are)

Some scholars conclude that this is a problem that can be fixed by turning to more democratic and secularized system of board leadership of institutions, such as that adopted by Shambhala, rather than relying on charismatic teachers.³⁷ However, devotion (T. *depé*; W. *dad pa*; S. *prasāda. śraddhā*) to the guru is an essential aspect of the Tibetan Buddhist system and cannot be removed without fundamentally changing the Vajrayāna. In *Words of my Perfect Teacher*, Patrul Orgyen Jikmé Chökyi Wangpo (better known as ‘Patrul Rinpoche,’ 1808–87) explains that without faith and devotion in one’s teacher, one cannot see the truth, and thus one cannot attain Buddhahood.

After explaining how to examine a teacher before taking him as one’s guru, and listing several types of teacher to avoid – including those that break their Buddhist vows, or who think they are enlightened just because they are descended from well-known lamas, and those who emulate crazy wisdom without having any real enlightened qualities – Patrul Rinpoche explains how to follow the lama:

To follow the teacher, you should have so much confidence in him that you perceive him as a real Buddha...Your outlook should be so broad that you can accept whatever your teacher and spiritual companions may do. You should be so generous that you can give the teacher whatever you possess. Your perception of everything should be pure, not always critical and tainted...However incomprehensibly the teacher may behave, always maintain pure perception, and recognize his way of doing things as his skilful methods.³⁸

The same book, a standard introductory text for students of Tibetan Buddhism, especially the earlier schools, contains many stories of lamas behaving at least as outrageously as Trungpa and Sogyal and indeed, the crazy wisdom tradition has a long and venerated history in these schools of Tibetan

‘perfect living Buddhas,’” Chandler, *Enthralled*, 1–2. It appears that in Rigpa, such brainwashing was institutionalised, so that any one who expressed doubts about Sogyal Lakar was sent to a “therapist,” “whose job involved convincing the doubters that it was their error of judgement because they lacked ‘pure vision’ – or [that] by criticising Sogyal they were in breach of samaya.” Finnegan and Hogendoorn, *Sex and Violence*, 162.

37 Sandra Bell, “Scandals in Emerging Western Buddhism,” in *Westward Dharma: Buddhism beyond Asia*, eds. Charles S. Prebish and Martin Baumann, (Berkeley: University of California Press, 2002), 238.

38 Patrul Rinpoche, *Words of My Perfect Teacher: A Complete Translation of a Classic Introduction to Tibetan Buddhism*, rev. ed., trans. The Padmakara Translation Group, with a foreword by the Dalai Lama, (New Delhi: Vistaar Publications, 1999), 137–145.

Buddhism,³⁹ especially the Nyingma and Kagyu, with which both Shambhala and Rigpa are associated. Indeed, Trungpa authored a book called *Crazy Wisdom*, where he explains the eight manifestations of Guru Padmasambhava – an 8th Century Indian scholar and adept, widely regarded as the Buddha of Tibet – as manifestations of this crazy wisdom, which he describes as a state of ‘primordial innocence.’ Being enlightened, in the Tibetan tantric tradition, according to Trungpa, is not a matter of appearing old and wise, but rather as young and free.⁴⁰

Trungpa made the term famous in the West; however, crazy wisdom had been a well-established concept in Tibet for centuries. One story which is often told, involves Naropa (1016–1100), who was Chancellor at Nalanda university, and who gave up his position to seek tantric teachings from his prophesized teacher Tilopa (988–1069). Tilopa proceeded to put Naropa through the ‘twelve great hardships’ which involved jumping off a roof, jumping into fire, letting himself be used as a bridge across a river, being pierced multiple times, being beaten for stealing and for mistreating royalty on Tilopa’s command, and other instructions which would certainly raise eyebrows today.⁴¹ Yet, Tilopa was able to magically heal his student each time, and Naropa never considered his treatment as abusive.

Perhaps the most famous masters of crazy wisdom are the three madmen of roughly the 16th Century – the Madman of U (*Dbus-smyon*), the madman of Tsang (*Gtsang smyon*), and Drukpa Kunley (*Brug-smyon*).⁴² The madmen of U and of Tsang were known for wearing garments made of human remains.⁴³ Drukpa Kunley, seen as the reincarnation of the Indian Saraha (c.8th Century), another ‘divine madman,’⁴⁴ was known for his irreverence and magical powers.

39 There are four main schools of Tibetan Buddhism. Chronologically, these are, the *Nyingma* or ‘Old Translation’ school (8th Century), the *Kagyu* or ‘Oral Transmission’ school (11th Century) and *Sakya*, literally ‘Pale Earth’ school (11th Century), and the reformist *Gelug* ‘Virtuous’ school of the Dalai Lamas (14th Century).

40 Chögyam Trungpa, *Crazy Wisdom*, (Boulder, CO: Shambhala Publications, 1991), 25–26.

41 Khenpo Könchog Gyaltzen, *The Great Kagyu Masters: The Golden Lineage Treasury* (New York: Snow Lion Publications, 1990), 55–80.

42 John Ardussi and Lawrence Epstein, “The Saintly Madman in Tibet,” in *Himalayan Anthropology: The Indo-Tibetan Interface*, ed. James F. Fisher, (The Hague: Mouton Publishers, 1978), 331; see also David M. DiValerio, *The Holy Madmen of Tibet*, (New York: Oxford University Press, 2015).

43 DiValerio, *Holy Madmen*, 1, 24.

44 Keith Dowman (trans.), *The Divine Madman: The Sublime Life and Songs of Drukpa Kunley*, (Varanasi: Pilgrims Publishing, 2000), 26.

Among his many miraculous displays he is said to have slaughtered animals just to reanimate them.⁴⁵ Yet the most often cited facts about Kunley are his multiple sexual exploits; it is said that Bhutanese men would offer their wives and daughters in marriage.⁴⁶

Stories such as these are well known and have been celebrated from the very beginning of Tibetan Buddhism in the West as we have seen. Yet, in 1993, a meeting was convened in Dharamsala, between a group of Western Buddhists and the Dalai Lama, where the problem was brought up that some Western female students thought they needed to sleep with their lamas in order to show proper devotion. The Western nun Tenzin Palmo explained that very often requests for sex were taken as a manifestation of crazy wisdom to which the Dalai Lama replied with a somewhat dismissive comment. He emphasised that monks and nuns are not allowed to engage in sexual practices, or to take alcohol or drugs, but that only those who have ‘deep insight,’ or ‘wisdom’ might engage in such practices, adding “I don’t know if (such insight) is crazy or not.”⁴⁷

Followers of the earlier traditions of Tibetan Buddhism are able to dismiss this as a particularity of the Dalai Lama’s Gelug tradition, which took a somewhat reformist approach in the 14th century. In Tibetan Buddhism, there is no central authority like the Catholic Pope who can issue universal decrees, and at that same meeting, the Dalai Lama insisted that the various Tibetan Buddhist schools must remain independent.⁴⁸ Indeed, the crazy wisdom tradition is still strong today, as we have seen, most notably in Shambhala and Rigpa.

Ösel Tendzin had been empowered by Trungpa into the crazy wisdom tradition and Stephen Butterfield, a student of his, explains how his actions might be interpreted. According to Butterfield, the “disaster” Tendzin had caused in knowingly spreading the HIV virus, or, indeed, any other disaster “could be used as a vehicle for teaching dharma.” Indeed, Butterfield explains his motivation in writing about the matter as honouring what his teacher Tendzin had given him by applying it to him. He explains further:

From a Vajrayana point of view, passion, aggression, and ignorance, the sources of human suffering, are also the wellsprings of enlightenment.

45 Divalerio, *Holy Madmen*, 194.

46 Dowman, *Divine Madman*, 129, 164.

47 Dalai Lama, “Dalai Lama on consort practice and crazy wisdom,” 1993, YouTube video, 3:50, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HScZ1rLBfz8&t=358s>

48 Lama, “Consort Practice,” 9:08; 9:54; 10:56.

Afflictions like AIDS are not merely disasters, but accelerations toward wisdom, and opportunities to wake up. They can be transformed into buddha-mind.⁴⁹

Whether true or not, the dangers of this sort of statement should be quite clear. If any kind of abusive behaviour by a lama can be justified as an “acceleration towards wisdom” and “an opportunity to wake up,” then this seems to give license to all sorts of misbehaviour by lamas and to invalidate victims’ complaints. Moreover, it makes the Vajrayāna Buddhist faith appear cultish and degenerate. I will go on to argue that such sentiments, even if honestly held by Vajrayāna followers, should never be made public, if Tibetan Buddhism is to survive in today’s world.

Analysis⁵⁰

The encounter between the post-traditional and modern understanding of Buddhism as a science, and traditional Asian Buddhism with its belief in magic and merit-making, has brought about a third, perhaps more reflective form of Buddhism, which seeks to undo even those vestiges of colonialism that require Buddhism to fit into the straightjacket of modern values and epistemology⁵¹ in order to be accepted as a World Religion. Known as global or glocal Buddhism, it is both global and local; global because contemporary Buddhist Institutions generally span continents and there are few genuinely independent, local Buddhist centres in Europe and America. At the same time, local branches of these global Buddhist organisations often intentionally adapt to local culture and customs, embracing the particular challenges of the place.⁵²

It is clear that if Tibetan Buddhism is to flourish in the contemporary world, it may need to adapt to local conditions. This is important particularly for those schools that not only accept but seem to be centred upon the notion of crazy wisdom. For reasons of legality and public perception, lamas cannot expect to get away with beating, raping and otherwise abusing their students in the modern world.

49 Butterfield, *The Double Mirror*, 6–7.

50 Most of this section is drawn from the oral teachings and published work of Dzongsar Jamyang Khyentse Rinpoche, in particular *The Guru Drinks Bourbon?* (Boulder, Colorado: Shambhala, 2016).

51 For more on the epistemological dimension of Buddhism, see Colette Sciberras, “Faith, reason or superstition? Reclaiming Guru Devotion as a form of knowing” in Pranav Kumar, *Bharatiya Knowledge Traditions*, Vol. V, (Delhi; Motilal Banarsidass, Forthcoming).

52 Jørn Borup, “Buddhism and Globalization.” In *Oxford Research Encyclopedias of Religion*, ed. John Barton (2021), 7–10.

At the same time, it will not do to dilute the Vajrayāna in order to suit the modern world. This has been made quite clear by many lamas, most notably Dzongsar Jamyang Khyentse Rinpoche (a.k.a ‘Khyentse Norbu,’ b. 1961), who has addressed in several places the issues regarding Chögyam Trungpa and Sogyal Lakar.

To begin with, Khyentse emphasises that the Vajrayāna is not for everyone and that there are plenty of other Buddhist paths which are perfectly complete in themselves. As he points out, samaya can be compared to marriage⁵³ and the guru to a benevolent dictator.⁵⁴ Students need to enter this commitment as though they were entering in a relationship of “submissive bondage.”⁵⁵ This is not something to be undertaken lightly and certainly not something to be publicized to all and sundry. Prospective students need to check their motivation and ask themselves whether they are truly ready to do anything this guru asks or whether they might just be looking for a group to identify with.

The relationship between a tantric guru and his or her students can be expected to be quite difficult because it is the guru’s job to “pull the rug away from under [a student’s] feet.”⁵⁶ Our expectations and assumptions prevent us from awakening, and so the guru will at some point disappoint and even shock us. It is the only way to break through students’ pre-conceptions so that they will experience the vastness of the enlightened mind. Indeed without a proper foundation of understanding the view, all the tantric meditations, methods, and substances could create a disturbance in students because many of these methods are designed to be politically incorrect and are not meant to complement the conventional way of thinking.⁵⁷

Again, if students are not prepared to be disturbed and to have their ego and expectations crushed, there are safer, less seemingly painful Buddhist paths.

Unfortunately, such warnings generally tend to be counter-productive; the more it is emphasised that the Vajrayāna is a dangerous path and not for everyone, the more appealing it seems to become. Thus, it also needs to be emphasised that one does not receive empowerments or initiations (*S. abhiṣeka*, *T. wang*, *W. dbang*) simply by being present for the ceremony. Indeed, only

53 Khyentse, *The Guru Drinks Bourbon?* 17, 59.

54 *Ibid.*, 20.

55 *Ibid.*, 19.

56 *Ibid.*, 37.

57 *Ibid.*, 139.

those who “consciously request and receive an initiation and deliberately enter into that mandala” can be said to have entered into a Vajrayāna relationship with the guru.⁵⁸ The Dalai Lama similarly explains that although initiations are often given to thousands of people at a time, very few truly receive the empowerment, since this requires following a highly detailed sequence of visualisations as well as some understanding of the principles of tantra.⁵⁹

Most beginners barely know what it means to receive empowerments and enter a mandala, but at the very least, one might say it should involve something extraordinary, perhaps even magical or miraculous. If nothing out of the ordinary has been experienced, then perhaps no real empowerment has been received and students do not need to worry about breaking their samaya with the lama who has bestowed it.

Although it is good practice, even when one has not truly received an empowerment, to try to see the lama as a Buddha and to refrain from criticizing him or her openly, until one has seen something truly special, there is no need to follow a guru blindly. Indeed,

If a guru asks you to do something and you can't do it for whatever reason, you should know that you are allowed to say no. And that guru has a responsibility to not insist. If you really can't obey and the guru insists, it is the guru who is creating the seed of breaking samaya.⁶⁰

Once empowerment has truly been received, then the details of what goes on between a lama and a samaya-holding student automatically become secret. Having experienced something magical, students tend to regard that experience and the guru who bestowed it as completely sacred and infinitely precious, so that they do not throw around the guru's name lightly, let alone reveal the goings on between them.

In fact, the Vajrayāna, in its earliest stages in India, was practiced in utmost secrecy (*S. guhya*; *T. sang pa*; *W. gsang pa*). This was perhaps due to sectarian friction and rampant militarization,⁶¹ as a “series of religious strategies developed

58 Ibid., 57.

59 Dalai Lama, “Dalai Lama's reply to Tenzin Palmo” 1993, YouTube video, 5:47, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=c-1hfSmwuYE&list=PLcho93L85QwGCerd36eRsF2PSevcvysTX>

60 Khyentse, *The Guru Drinks Bourbon?*, 149.

61 Ronald M. Davidson, “The problem of secrecy in Indian Tantric Buddhism,” in *The Culture of Secrecy in Japanese Religion*, eds. Bernhard Scheid and Mark Teeuwen (New York: Routledge, 2006), 59.

by communities to avoid obliteration in the militarized environment of the period.”⁶² Whatever the origins of secrecy in Indian tantra, according to modern Tibetans the reasons for it are, first, that the uninitiated might develop wrong view (T. *log ta*. W. *log lta*), that is, people might think badly about Buddhism.⁶³ This is a strong argument for why public pronouncements such as Butterfield’s cited above should never be made. The general public does not have the sort of faith in gurus that could enable them to understand such a claim, and the most likely outcome is outrage and censure.

A second reason for secrecy is that Vajrayāna is widely regarded as dangerous. As we have seen, the crazy wisdom tradition, and the Vajrayāna in general, often involve acts that would appear to go against conventional morality and law. Yet the difficulties that might result from its unauthorized use are not just what you might expect from engaging in unconventional or illegal behaviour, but also said to be the wrath of highly realised deities (S. *dharmapāla*; T. *chökyong*; W. *chos skyong*) who are committed to protecting the Buddhist teachings, and often inflict mental and physical illness or other disasters upon transgressors.⁶⁴ Sharing tantric secrets with the uninitiated can also result in rebirth for both in Vajra Hell, a space reserved for those who break their samaya. The worst crime a samaya-breaker can commit is to turn against his or her lama.

It should be clear by now that the Vajrayāna does not conform to modern, rationalist and secular criteria of truth and morality, nor does it pretend to. Yet, if a student experiences a lama’s behaviour as abusive, he or she is most probably operating under these assumptions, and has not really entered into the Vajrayāna path at all. Most probably, such a student has had the misfortune to encounter a charlatan. In such a case, there is no samaya involved, and as the Dalai Lama pointed out, the abuse can and ought to be exposed.

The only way to break one’s samaya is to have seen the guru as a Buddha, as the nature of one’s mind, and later on to decide to ignore that experience and turn against the guru. Again, this is not something that can be done accidentally or without knowledge.

Finally, it needs to be understood that samaya will be broken and can be repaired. As Khyentse explains:

62 Ibid., 74.

63 Urmila Nair, “Beyond the Secret (*gsang ba*): The Performativity of Citation in an Exile Tibetan Buddhist Ritual,” *Signs and Society*, 12, no 2, (spring 2024), 151, 142–163.

64 Ibid., 152.

To even think you are a man or a woman, let alone to think you are ugly or beautiful, is breaking Vajrayāna samaya. To consider your five aggregates (i.e. your body, feelings, perceptions, volitions and consciousness) as ordinary is violating the Vajrayāna samaya. To look at a place like Lucerne and think it's a clean and beautiful land in contrast to Beijing is breaking samaya. A tantric practitioner's sole aim is to see everything as pure and immeasurable.⁶⁵

Clearly, even if one has had a glimpse of the truth from a lama, it is unlikely that one will immediately enter a perpetual state of non-duality where everything is seen as pure and immeasurable. There is an assumption that keeping samaya perfectly is something that needs to be practiced and that is only perfected at the later stages of the path. Thus, prospective students of the Vajrayāna need to be wary of claims, from other students, or, worse, from gurus, that expressing any doubt about a guru constitutes a break in samaya. To reiterate, if one has truly received empowerment, one will be left with no doubt that the guru is not an ordinary being. Until one reaches such certainty, it is impossible to break samaya.

At this point, readers may wonder why anyone would be attracted to the Vajrayana path, given its inherent dangers. Why not stick to reading *sutras* and commentaries and limiting one's devotional practices to representations of the Buddha, Dharma and Sangha, rather than to a human guru who is expected to cause trouble for you? The value of such a path is that it allows a practitioner to see the truth via a personal intermediary, for whom one has generated devotion. It is difficult to relate spiritually to abstract philosophical concepts such as 'emptiness' (S. *śūnyatā*), or 'luminosity' (S. *prabhāsvara*) and since religious faith is affective as well as cognitive, it is easier to relate to the truth when the truth is personified. Another way of expressing the truth in Tibetan Buddhism, is to say that the Buddha is the nature of your own mind. The lama, in Tibetan Buddhism, is able to directly introduce the student to the Buddha as the nature of their own mind. And yet it is generally understood that without some faith in and devotion to the lama, the student will not get it.

As we have seen, lamas also have at their disposal several means of increasing their students' faith and devotion. In the Tibetan hagiographies, it will be recalled, there are splendid accounts of various miracles witnessed by the masses. Thus, modern students of Tibetan Buddhism should understand that having faith and devotion should mean that even if one does not yet fully see

65 Khyentse, *The Guru Drinks Bourbon?*, 180–181. Insert added.

the truth at all times, then at least one should have witnessed something special as a result of the lama's teachings and behaviour. Having faith and devotion does not simply mean refusing to condemn a lama or express one's doubts. If a student does not at least see something that could be described as 'magical' as well as 'abusive,' then either the lama is a fake, or else, one does not really have faith and devotion. In either case, it would be good to drop the pretense.

Summary

I hope to have shown that Tibetan Buddhism does not easily fit the categories of post-traditional or post-secular, but contains a glorious mixture of pre-modern, modern and post-modern elements. The lack of awareness about all of these different elements in Tibetan Buddhism has given rise to abuse, misunderstanding and scandal, and the teacher-student relationship is almost expected to upset modern sensibilities and assumptions. To preserve what is valuable in Tibetan Buddhism will require better understanding of what it means to enter samaya with a guru, and a commitment to keeping tantric goings on secret. Most importantly, students must understand that the tantric lama is not an ordinary being and they must not allow their expectations of him or her to be curtailed by modern beliefs about the possibility or otherwise of magic.

Abbreviations

AN *Aṅguttara Nikaya*

P. Pāli

S. Sanskrit

T. Tibetan

W. Wylie

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